

A Human Fingertip Finite Element Model for Simulation of Haptic Interactions

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Abstract — The human ability to assess the properties of objects and surfaces via touch is mediated by the complex mechanical behavior of the hand soft tissues at contact. Touch-sensitive neurons placed in the human skin activate in response to local deformation of the skin itself, resulting in what we understand as tactile perception. We set out to develop a new Finite Element model of the human hand, specifically designed to simulate its biomechanics in the context of haptic contact, to investigate its underexplored aspects, which can open to an informed design of robotic tactile sensors and human-machine interfaces. In this work, we present the design of a Finite Element model of the human fingertip, the validation of its mechanical behaviour with respect to available biomechanical data, and its use in the simulation of a softness discrimination task. We investigated the response of the fingertip to contact with objects of different compliance, to retrieve insights on how humans are able to perceive softness.

Keywords— *finite element analysis, tactile perception, haptic contact, touch interactions, biomechanical modelling*

I. INTRODUCTION

The complex relationship between the mechanical stimuli arising in the context of haptic interactions and the perceived tactile properties, such as softness, friction and shape, remains underexplored. Mechanoreceptors placed in the human dermis (an inner layer of the skin) activate in response to local mechanical straining of the surrounding tissues, and the generated signals are encoded by the brain into a variety of superficial properties of the touched surface [1]. This perceptual process is mediated by the complex biomechanical behaviour of the human hand itself, with its multiple layers of soft tissues that exhibit highly nonlinear properties. Shining light on these mechanisms could offer a backdoor for an informed design of tactile sensors for robotic hands, as well as of effective interfaces for advanced human-robot interaction.

Finite Element (FE) analysis is a widespread method for the simulation of physical phenomena described by nonlinear, multivariate differential equations. Numerous studies have presented FE models of human hands and fingers, for the specific purpose of modelling their behaviour during haptic contact interactions [2]. However, a variety of underexplored topics could be investigated further through this instrument. We developed a FE model of a human finger, and compared its behaviour against a series of experimental data. Here, we discuss the design of the model and its validation. We then describe an example of its application in the simulation of a softness discrimination task, drawing a comparison between the simulated results and known observations on haptic softness discrimination tasks in humans [3].

II. METHODS

This section details the design and validation of a FE fingertip model, as well as preliminary results obtained from simulations of haptic contact interactions.

A. Finite Element fingertip model

A FE model of a human fingertip, specifically the distal phalanx of an index finger, was developed using the FE software *Ansys*. The geometry of the fingertip and the separation between its different biological tissues were designed according to average sizes in humans. The fingertip is composed of five different materials: bone, nail, two skin layers (epidermis and dermis) and a subcutaneous mass, as shown in Fig. 1. Elastic constitutive properties were assigned to each material with parameters taken from the literature, using hyperelastic models for the soft tissues (epidermis, dermis and subcutaneous). Shared topology meshing was used to guarantee bonded behaviour at all tissue interfaces, and the mesh was refined in the finger pad, to better capture its behaviour under contact.

B. Validation of the FE model

To verify the accuracy of the biomechanical behaviour of the model with respect to the real anatomy, quasi-static compression of the fingertip against flat, rough surfaces was simulated, using the values of normal force and friction from [4]. In [4], 18 subjects were asked to grasp a device between their thumb and index finger, compressing the fingers against two rough, flat surfaces, to perform a manipulation task. Two different rough interfaces were used, a “low” and a “high” friction one, each characterized by a dynamic friction coefficient calculated as a negative exponential of the normal contact force. For each repetition of the task, contact force in both the tangential and the normal direction and superficial strains were measured. To simulate this task using our FE fingertip model, we simulated the compression of the fingertip against a flat surface, imposing an external force using the sequence of normal force measurements taken from [4]. A symmetry plane was added at the bottom of the flat object, simulating the presence of the other finger, not included in the model. The dynamic friction coefficient values were calculated using the provided exponential laws, and applied to the target surface. Results concerning the contact area on the fingertip as a function of the contact force were compared with sigmoidal functions, fitted on the average contact area values retrieved for each repetition of the task.

Fig. 1. View in longitudinal section of the developed Finite Element model of the human fingertip. The biological tissues are shown in different colors, each

corresponding to a different constitutive model. Mesh elements are smaller in the area interested by contact.

C. Softness discrimination example

The fingertip model, validated according to the described criteria, was used to simulate a task of compliance discrimination as performed by humans, to investigate the mechanical response induced in its soft tissues by the haptic interaction. Five silicone samples were produced such that a human could easily discern their softness by pressing a finger on their surface, similar to what was described in [5]. To accurately simulate their behaviour, force-displacement curves were obtained by compressing each sample with a flat, rigid indenter, mounted on the end-effector of a 7 DOF Franka Emika Panda manipulator. Indentation displacements were retrieved using the robot kinematics, while the normal force was measured using an ATI 6-axis force/torque sensor mounted behind the indenter. Hyperelastic material models for each of the silicones were selected based on the force-displacement curves, using the *CurveFit* tool within *Ansys*. Pressing of the FE fingertip model against a slab of each silicone type was simulated, assuming low friction, i.e., a constant coefficient of 0.01. The fingertip was constrained such that it could only translate normal to the surface, and a ramped contact force of 3 N was imposed. The simulations were performed under quasi-static conditions, assuming slow indentation of the fingertip.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validation of the FE fingertip model was carried out as described in II.B. 8 simulations were performed, using contact force and friction coefficient values taken from 4 of the subjects, considering for each subject a “low” friction and a “high” friction test. For each simulation, the resulting contact area was plotted as a function of the normal force, and compared with the average values for each subject-surface pair from [4]. The average discrepancy between simulated and measured contact areas across the entirety of the simulations was of 17%, and the final areas differed by 4.5%. The results for one of the 8 simulations are shown in Fig. 2.

Estimated contact areas as a function of normal contact force were also extracted from the simulated compressions against the silicone samples, as shown in Fig. 3. The growth rate of simulated interactions, both the average and the maximum slope of the contact area (i.e., its derivative over contact force) the fingertip contact area over contact force is a known cue for softness perception in humans [3]. In accordance to this, in the

Fig. 2. Comparison between the contact force-area curves obtained via FE simulation (in red) and experimentally (in blue). The experimental data is represented as a sigmoid fit on the raw data, considering all the trials of one of the 4 subjects interacting with the higher-friction surface.

Fig. 3. Contact force-area plots for simulated pressing of the fingertip against the five modeled silicone specimens. The darker colour indicates a softer silicone, i.e., lower stiffness, resulting in a higher slope of the curve.

were shown to increase for increasing softness of the touched silicone. Growth rates in the five simulations were shown to be statistically different (Kruskal-Wallis test, $p < 0.005$).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

We presented the design of a FE model of a human fingertip, and its validation by comparing its mechanical behaviour under contact with experimental data from human trials. We simulated a simple haptic discrimination task using the FE model, retrieving preliminary results on potential cues used to discriminate softness. A comparison was carried out with the paradigm described in [3], in which the growth rate of the contact area was observed to be a good predictor for the human ability to discriminate softness. Further investigation into the mechanical stress-strain state induced in the fingertip model during the contact interactions may be beneficial, providing deeper insights into how humans are able to identify softness and other surface properties such as friction. To achieve this, a more detailed FE model may be required, which takes into account dynamic effects of the interaction and integrates biomechanical properties that were neglected here, such as those of the finger joints. We plan to expand the model to include the entirety of the human index finger, to be able to simulate generalized haptic interactions as performed by humans.

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